

New management practices in rainfed olive groves

Introduction

In great part of Southern Europe, where olive trees are grown it is expected the rise of temperatures, less precipitation with bigger periodicity, that can be characterized by less rainy days however with more precipitation, and the increase of extreme natural events, such as droughts.

To combat the effects of the climate change new management practices must be explored and applied. Seven objectives were proposed to be accomplished, they were:

1. Comparing the effect of different herbaceous soil compositions versus the control of spontaneous plant growth;
2. Assessing the effects of different biologic residues applied as compost/fertilizer;
3. Evaluating the use of Bio-stimulants for the plants, this meaning the use of fungi and bacteria in a symbiotic relation with the plant;
4. Assessing the genetic varieties of olive trees in Portugal, and categorise them by their adaption the climatic conditions;
5. Evaluating the effect of using different chemical substances in the induction of drought resistance mechanisms.

The data collected in the experiments allowed the creation of scientific articles, technical articles, university thesis and outreach sessions. In the end all the information is going to be resumed in a “Manual of good practices”, this document is not yet created because some of the trials are still running.

To measure the efficiency of the different studied management practices, in all the experiments different parameters were measured related to the tree physiology, growth, the properties of the soil and the quality of the produced fruit and oil.

From the results available to this day, we can take some conclusions. In relation to soil cover management practices, taking in mind the climate change and the normal site conditions (Mediterranean climate, soils with low quality and depth), they should allow the development of herbaceous vegetation in the Winter (increasing the organic matter present in the soil and decreasing the risk of erosion) and limit the expansion of the vegetation from the beginning of the Spring, in this way controlling the competition for water. From the

different management practices studied, two of them comply with the objective explained above. The use of leguminous plants soil cover with a short cycle allows the protection of the soil from erosion, the increase in organic matter, the increase in nitrogen deposition, and at the same time since it as a short cycle the competition for water does not occur in the driest period. The use of herbicide after the spontaneous vegetation sprouts, in the beginning of the Spring, also add the best results since it fulfils the objectives of soil protection and reduced water competition. The most common soil management practice, low depth tillage, didn't fulfil the criteria since it cuts the roots of the trees reducing their capacity to absorb water, and at long term it decreases the quality of the soil, since it becomes more susceptible to erosion.

In relation to the use of mycorrhizae fungi, it was verified the increase in plant growth and resilience to dry condition. This was achieved because this symbiotic relationship allows an increase in nutrient mobilisation inside the soil and bigger water capturing area (since the mycelium net works as a "second root system" for the plant). Other benefits are the decrease of the impact from toxicity of heavy metals and the increase tolerance of plants to the soil salinity. The use of nitrogen fixation microorganisms had good results, allowing an increase of available nitrogen present in the soil.

The use of abscisic acid (ABA) as a foliar pre-treatment had good results in increasing drought tolerance and recovery capacity. Under water deficit conditions, ABA is responsible to control stomatal closure, hydraulic conductivity, and root development. When applied to the leaves of the plant, it attenuated the drought induced decline in biomass production, induced root growth and enhanced water use efficiency.

Lessons learned

In Portugal one of the productions that is going to be most affected by the climate change is the olive production, since most, around 90%, of the area of this trees species are grown in rainfed systems. The shift in climate conditions is expected to impact the physiology of the trees, reducing their production, increasing the variability of annual production, and increasing the severity of the damages caused by pests and diseases.

Finding an alternative solution such as irrigation is not a feasible solution since the availability and quality of water is going to decrease in the coming years. The solution is to use management practices compatible with the climate, that increase the performance of the production systems, maintain/increase the soil qualities, and keep the trees in good vigour, decreasing their susceptibility to pest and diseases.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/new-practices-rainfed-olive-groves-strategies-mitigation-and-adaptation-climate-change_en

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